

A Study on the Knowledge and Practices of Menstrual Hygiene Among the Adolescent GirlsVidya Mallesh¹, Shivaraj B M², Varada Vidya Rani³, Pandurangaya R⁴, Shashank K⁵¹Department of Community Medicine, CIMS Chikkamagalur, Karnataka²Associate Professor, Department of Community Medicine, CIMS Chikkamagalur, Karnataka³Paediatrician, Aralaguppe Mallegowda District Hospital, Chikkamagaluru⁴Assistant Professor, Department of Obstetrics & Gynaecology, CIMS Chikkamagaluru⁵Associate Professor, Department of Community Medicine, CIMS Chikkamagalur, Karnataka

Received: 25-05-2024 / Revised: 15-06-2024 / Accepted: 01-07-2024

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Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:

Background: Menstrual hygiene management is crucial for the health and well-being of adolescent girls, yet practices and knowledge often vary based on demographic and socio-economic factors. This study aims to explore these dynamics among 285 adolescent students in Karnataka, considering their age, educational levels, family structure, and parental backgrounds.

Methods: A cross-sectional study was conducted using structured questionnaires to collect data on demographic variables (age, class, religion, family type), parental characteristics (education, occupation), knowledge about menstruation, hygiene practices, and disposal methods of menstrual materials. Data were analyzed using descriptive statistics and chi-square tests to determine associations between demographic factors and menstrual hygiene practices.

Results: The majority of participants were under 16 years old (73%), with Hindus comprising the largest religious group (61.8%) and nuclear families being predominant (77.5%). Adolescents aged 16 or older exhibited higher rates of good hygiene practices (83.1%) compared to younger peers (59.1%, $p = 0.0001$). Similarly, Hindus (80.1%) showed better practices than Muslims (38.6%, $p < 0.0001$) and others (87.5%, $p < 0.0001$). Maternal education and nuclear family settings correlated positively with improved hygiene practices ($p = 0.147$ to $p < 0.0001$).

Conclusion: The study highlights the influence of demographic and socio-economic factors on menstrual hygiene practices among adolescents. Targeted interventions are needed to enhance knowledge and practices, especially among younger students, Muslims, and those from lower educational backgrounds.

Keywords: Menstrual hygiene, adolescence, demographic factors, education, socio-economic status.

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Introduction

Menstrual hygiene management is a crucial aspect of health education for adolescent girls, influencing their physical, psychological, and social well-being. Adolescence, a transformative phase marked by significant physiological changes, is defined by the World Health Organization (WHO) as the period between 10 and 19 years of age [1].

This phase is pivotal as it marks the shift from childhood to adulthood. Globally, around 1.9 billion women of reproductive age menstruate, and among them, adolescent girls represent a vulnerable group [2]. In India, adolescents constitute approximately 21% of the population. The onset of menstruation is a significant event in a girl's life but is often accompanied by taboos and societal constraints, leading to negative perceptions and considering it unhygienic [3]. How girls learn

about menstruation can significantly influence their reaction to menarche. Educating about menstruation and hygiene should commence early and remain a crucial part of health education throughout their lives [4]. However, many girls receive this information only after experiencing menarche, leading to inadequate menstrual hygiene management. Poor hygiene practices escalate the risk of reproductive tract infections (RTIs), which can lead to severe complications if untreated, especially in young adolescent girls [5].

In many developing countries, including India, cultural stigmas and lack of education about menstruation result in inadequate menstrual hygiene management [6]. This situation is exacerbated by the lack of access to affordable and hygienic menstrual products, clean water, and

proper sanitation facilities [7]. The consequences of poor menstrual hygiene can be far-reaching, including infections, absenteeism from school, and long-term reproductive health issues [7].

Traditional beliefs and societal norms in India often perpetuate silence around menstruation, resulting in limited knowledge and awareness among adolescent girls [8]. Schools, which should serve as a primary source of health education, frequently lack comprehensive programs addressing menstrual hygiene management. Consequently, many girls resort to unhygienic practices, such as using old rags or other unsafe materials, leading to health complications and reduced quality of life [8].

Recent initiatives by various governmental and non-governmental organizations have aimed to improve menstrual hygiene management through education and distribution of sanitary products [9]. However, significant gaps in knowledge and practice remain among adolescent girls, particularly in rural and underserved areas [10]. Understanding the current state of menstrual hygiene practices and the associated knowledge among this demographic is essential for developing targeted interventions that can effectively address these gaps.

Given this context, the current study aimed to evaluate the understanding and habits concerning menstrual hygiene among adolescent girls attending government schools in Chikkamagaluru. By identifying the prevalent practices and the level of awareness, this research seeks to inform policy and programmatic efforts to enhance menstrual health education and accessibility to hygienic menstrual products. In doing so, it aspires to contribute to the broader goal of improving health outcomes and quality of life for adolescent girls.

Materials and Methods

Study Design and Setting: This cross-sectional study was conducted under the department of Community Medicine as a part of awareness program regarding menstrual hygiene among the school children in collaboration with pediatric and obg departments of CIMS medical college Chikkamagaluru, after obtaining the ethical approval, study was conducted for 3 months from January to March 2024. during 3 months from January to March 2024.

Study Population: The study population consisted of all female students from Basavanahalli Government Girls High School, specifically those in the 8th to 10th standards, aged between 10-18 years. Only students willing to participate in the study were included.

Students who had medical conditions affecting menstrual cycles, recent menstrual irregularities, language barriers, recent participation in similar

studies, and significant changes in hygiene practices, were excluded from the study.

Sample Size: There are a total of 400 students currently studying at the school. The sample size for this study was calculated using Cochran's formula for sample size estimation, considering a 95% confidence level, a 5% margin of error, and assuming a population proportion of 50%. Initially, the formula yielded $n_0=384$. Given the finite population of 400 students, the sample size was adjusted using the finite population correction formula to $n \approx 196$, accounting for potential non-responses or incomplete data. Therefore, the final sample size for the study was determined to be 285 students. A census sampling technique was employed, wherein all eligible students from the 8th to 10th standards who met the inclusion criteria were invited to participate in the study.

Data Collection: Data were collected using a pretested, structured questionnaire. The questionnaire was developed in English and translated into the local language, Kannada, to ensure comprehension. It consisted of sections on demographic information, knowledge about menstruation and menstrual hygiene, and menstrual hygiene practices (Menstrual material use, Handwashing, and Disposal of menstrual materials). The questionnaire was pretested in a pilot study with 10% participants ($n=20$) to ensure reliability and validity.

Data Analysis: Data were entered into Microsoft Excel and analyzed using SPSS version 25. Descriptive statistics such as frequencies, and percentages were used to summarize the data. Bivariate analysis was performed to assess the association between demographic variables and knowledge and practices related to menstrual hygiene. Chi-square tests were used for categorical variables. A p-value of <0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Ethical Considerations: Ethical approval was obtained from the Institutional Ethics Committee. Permission to conduct the study was also obtained from the Department of Education, Chikkamagaluru. Written informed consent was obtained from the parents or guardians of the participants, and assent was obtained from the participants themselves. Participants were assured of the confidentiality of their responses and the voluntary nature of their participation.

Results

The majority of participants were under 16 years old (73%), with a notable proportion aged 16 or more (27%). Regarding educational levels, participants were evenly distributed across 8th (33%), 9th (33%), and 10th (34%) grades. In terms of religious affiliation, Hindu participants

constituted the largest group (61.8%), followed by Muslim (35.4%) and others (2.9%). Most participants belonged to nuclear families (77.5%), with joint families accounting for 22.5% of the sample. Maternal education levels varied, with primary education being the most prevalent (56.5%), while maternal occupations were

predominantly home-makers (59%) and daily-wage laborers (23.9%). Paternal education mirrored maternal patterns, with primary education predominating (55.4%), while paternal occupations were primarily daily-wage laborers (59.3%) and agricultural laborers (16.1%) (Table 1).

Table 1: Demographic Distribution of Study Participants

Variables	Frequency	%
Age (years)		
<16	208	73
16 or more	77	27
Class		
8 th	94	33
9 th	94	33
10 th	97	34
Religion		
Hindu	176	61.8
Muslim	101	35.4
Others	8	2.9
Type of family		
Nuclear	221	77.5
Joint	64	22.5
Mother's Education		
No Formal Education	38	13.3
Primary education	161	56.5
Secondary Education	80	28.1
Graduate	6	2.1
Mother Occupation		
Home-maker	168	59
Daily-wage-labour	68	23.9
Agricultural-labour	25	8.8
Govt-worker	8	2.8
Private-worker	13	4.6
Business	3	1.1
Father Education level		
No Formal Education	55	19.3
Primary education	158	55.4
secondary Education	59	20.7
Graduate	8	2.9
Post Graduate	5	1.8
Fathers Occupation		
Stay at home	5	1.8
Daily-wage-labour	169	59.3
Agricultural-labour	46	16.1
Govt-worker	9	3.2
Private-worker	30	10.5
Business	26	9.1

A significant majority (80.4%) had heard about menstruation before experiencing their first period (menarche), primarily learning from mothers (39.6%) and media sources (30.2%). Most participants (69.8%) correctly perceived menstruation as a biological process, while a notable proportion (16.1%) viewed it as a disease or curse. Regarding understanding of the menstrual

cycle, 70.5% knew the typical duration (28-32 days), while 89.8% were aware of sanitary pads as menstrual hygiene products. Concerning hygiene practices, 80.4% knew correct practices such as frequent pad changes and handwashing, although 20.4% were unaware of health issues associated with poor menstrual hygiene. Information on menstrual hygiene primarily came from school

education programs (39.3%) and health care providers (24.9%). Awareness of social and cultural taboos surrounding menstruation was high, with

70.9% of participants indicating awareness within their community (Table 2).

Table 2: Knowledge and Awareness of Menstruation Among Study Participants

Knowledge Variable	Frequency	%
Have you heard about menstruation before experiencing your first period (menarche)?		
Yes	229	80.4
No	56	19.6
From whom did you primarily learn about menstruation?		
Mother	113	39.6
Teacher	44	15.4
Friends	42	14.7
Media	86	30.2
How do you perceive menstruation? Is it viewed as a		
Biological Process	199	69.8
Disease/Curse	46	16.1
Don't know	40	14.0
What do you understand about the menstrual cycle? Do you know the typical duration of a menstrual cycle (28-32 days), or do you have a different understanding?		
Correct (28-32 days)	201	70.5
Incorrect	84	29.5
Are you aware of different menstrual hygiene products? This includes		
Sanitary pads	256	89.8
Cloth	29	10.2
Others	14	4.9
Do you know the correct menstrual hygiene practices, such as changing pads frequently and washing hands? Or do you have incorrect beliefs or practices?		
Correct (e.g., changing pads frequently, washing hands)	229	80.4
Incorrect	56	19.6
Are you aware of health issues that can arise from poor menstrual hygiene practices?		
Yes	227	79.6
No	58	20.4
From where have you received information about menstrual hygiene?		
School education programs	112	39.3
Health care providers	71	24.9
Family members	57	20.0
Media	45	15.8
Are you aware of social and cultural taboos surrounding menstruation in your community?		
Aware	202	70.9
Not aware	83	29.1

Disposable sanitary pads were the most commonly used menstrual material both at home (38.2%) and away from home (78.6%), while cloth/towel usage was higher at home (47%) compared to when away (3.5%). A significant majority (86.3%) reported washing hands after changing menstrual materials,

with a similar proportion (80%) washing hands before. Most participants (78.9%) stored menstrual materials after their last period, often in cupboards (40.7%) or in the toilet/latrine room (29.8%). Wrapping in plastic bags (72.3%) was the most common method of disposal (Table 3).

Table 3: Menstrual Hygiene Practices Among Study Participants

Practices Variables	Frequency	%
The materials you used during menstruation when you were at home during your last menstrual period?		
Cloth/towel	134	47
Disposable sanitary pad	109	38.2
Reusable sanitary pad	39	13.7
Toilet paper	1	0.4
Cotton wool	1	0.4
Period underwear	1	0.4

What were all the materials you used during menstruation when you were away from home [at school/ work] during your last menstrual period?		
Cloth/towel	10	3.5
Disposable sanitary pad	224	78.6
Reusable sanitary pad	25	8.8
Toilet paper	1	0.4
Natural material (e.g., leaves, sand, grass)	6	2.1
Period underwear	3	1.1
Menstrual cup	2	0.7
No response	14	4.9
Did you wash and reuse any of your menstrual materials during your last menstrual period?		
Yes	108	37.9
No	177	62.1
During your last menstrual period, how many times did you change your menstrual material on the heaviest day of your period?		
1 time (wear until the next day)	14	4.9
2 times (eg. morning and evening)	68	23.9
3 times (eg. morning, evening and once during day)	105	36.8
4 times (eg. morning, evening, and twice during day)	82	28.8
No response	16	5.6
How often did you change your menstrual materials when you were away from your home [at school/ work] during your last menstrual period? (e.g., school, market, working outside the home)		
Never/no days	26	9.1
One day	85	29.8
Every day of my period	118	41.4
Some days	33	11.6
Did you wash your hands before changing your menstrual materials during your last menstrual period?		
Never	12	4.2
Sometimes	29	10.2
Every time	228	80
No response	16	5.6
Did you wash your hands after changing your menstrual materials during your last menstrual period?		
Never	4	1.4
Sometimes	21	7.4
Every time	246	86.3
No response	16	5.6
Where did you most often dispose of your used menstrual materials when you were at home during your last menstrual period?		
Into the latrine/toilet	30	10.5
Burned	51	17.9
Household rubbish (bin in latrine)	64	22.5
Household rubbish	24	8.4
Taken to community rubbish	19	6.7
Buried/bush/waterway	62	21.8
Did not dispose of any materials (including reusables)	3	1.1
Garbage disposal	1	0.4
Other	4	1.4
No response	27	9.5
Where did you most often dispose of your used menstrual materials when you were away from your home [at school/ work] during your last menstrual period?		
Transported home to dispose or reuse	2	0.7
Into the latrine/toilet	44	15.4
Bin in the latrine/toilet	176	61.8
Bin onsite but outside of the latrine/toilet	8	2.8
Community rubbish (not onsite)	9	3.2
Bush/buried/waterway	4	1.4
Burned	4	1.4
Anything	1	0.4

Other	4	1.4
No response	33	11.6
When disposing of your used menstrual materials, did you usually wrap them in anything?		
Yes, plastic bag, cover of pad	206	72.3
Yes, toilet paper	28	9.8
Yes, cloth	3	1.1
Yes, other	10	3.5
No	19	6.7
No response	19	6.7
After your last menstrual period, did you keep [store] your menstrual materials? (includes leftover disposables or reusables)		
Yes	225	78.9
No	36	12.6
No response	24	8.4
Where did you store your menstrual materials after your last menstrual period?		
Cupboard, cabinet or drawer	116	40.7
Under bed	30	10.5
In the toilet/latrine room	85	29.8
In a bathroom (not latrine/toilet)	41	14.4
Other area	1	0.4
Other room	2	0.7
Anything	5	1.8
Other	5	1.8
Did you store your menstrual materials inside any wrapping, packaging, or case?		
Wrapped in plastic or in plastic bag (including disposable pads in original packaging)	182	63.9
Wrapped in fabric or in a fabric bag	24	8.4
Wrapped in paper	33	11.6
Cardboard box	21	7.4
Other	2	0.7
No wrapping or container	3	1.1
No response	20	7

Significant differences were observed across various demographics. Participants aged 16 or more exhibited significantly higher rates of good menstrual hygiene practices (83.1%) compared to those under 16 years (59.1%, $p = 0.0001$). Similarly, Hindus (80.1%) showed better hygiene practices than Muslims (38.6%, $p < 0.0001$) and those of other religions (87.5%, $p < 0.0001$).

Higher education levels among mothers and nuclear family settings were also associated with better hygiene practices ($p = 0.147$ to $p < 0.0001$). Fathers' educational background and occupations showed varied impacts, with higher education and certain occupational roles correlating with improved hygiene practices (Table 4).

Table 4: Association between Demographic Variables and Menstrual Hygiene Practices.

Variable	Good (n=187)	Poor (n=98)	Total (n=285)	p-value
	Frequency (%)			
Age (years)				
<16	123 (59.1)	85 (40.9)	208	0.0001
16 or more	64 (83.1)	13 (16.9)	77	
Religion				
Hindu	141 (80.1)	35 (19.9)	176	<0.0001
Muslim	39 (38.6)	62 (61.4)	101	
Others	7 (87.5)	1 (12.5)	8	
Class				
8th	56 (59.6)	38 (40.4)	94	0.002
9th	54 (57.4)	40 (42.6)	94	
10th	77 (79.4)	20 (20.6)	97	
Type of Family				
Nuclear	164 (74.2)	57 (25.8)	221	<0.0001

Joint	23 (35.9)	41 (64.1)	64	
Mother's Education				
No Formal Education	21 (55.3)	17 (44.7)	38	0.147
Primary education	102 (63.4)	59 (36.6)	161	
Secondary Education	59 (73.8)	21 (26.3)	80	
Graduate	5 (83.3)	1 (16.7)	6	
Mother Occupation				
Home-maker	125 (74.4)	43 (25.6)	168	0.0003
Daily-wage-labour	35 (51.5)	33 (48.5)	68	
Agricultural-labour	18 (72.0)	7 (28.0)	25	
Govt-worker	4 (50.0)	4 (50.0)	8	
Private-worker	5 (38.5)	8 (61.5)	13	
Business	0 (0.0)	3 (100.0)	3	
Father Education level				
No Formal Education	28 (50.9)	27 (49.1)	55	0.013
Primary education	102 (64.6)	56 (35.4)	158	
Secondary Education	45 (76.3)	14 (23.7)	59	
Graduate	7 (96.4)	1 (3.6)	28	
Post Graduate	5 (100.0)	0 (0.0)	5	
Father Occupation				
Stay at home	1 (20.0)	4 (80.0)	5	0.074
Daily-wage-labour	110 (65.1)	59 (34.9)	169	
Agricultural-labour	27 (58.7)	19 (41.3)	46	
Govt-worker	6 (66.7)	3 (33.3)	9	
Private-worker	21 (70.0)	9 (30.0)	30	
Business	22 (84.6)	4 (15.4)	26	

Discussion

This study provides valuable insights into the factors influencing menstrual hygiene practices among adolescent participants, highlighting significant demographic variations and their implications for menstrual health education and interventions.

The study revealed several key findings regarding participants' knowledge and perceptions related to menstruation and menstrual hygiene. A significant majority (80.4%) had heard about menstruation before experiencing menarche, primarily learning from sources such as mothers (39.6%). Awareness of menstrual hygiene products was high, with 89.8% recognizing sanitary pads as appropriate products. Moreover, 80.4% demonstrated knowledge of correct menstrual hygiene practices, such as frequent pad changes and handwashing, while 79.6% were aware of health issues associated with poor menstrual hygiene. In a study by Mathiyalagen et al., 51.7% of respondents were not aware of menstruation before attaining menarche; 71.5% and 61.2% were not known about the cause and source of the menstrual bleeding, respectively [11]. A similar knowledge levels were assessed in the studies by Dudeja et al., and Jyothi et al., [12,13].

Approximately 65.6% of the 285 students in this study consistently demonstrated good menstrual hygiene practices. This conclusion is drawn from

their adherence to several key behaviors: 78.6% used disposable sanitary pads away from home, 65.6% changed menstrual materials at least three times on heavy days, 80% washed hands before changing, 86.3% washed hands after changing, 77.2% disposed of menstrual materials in latrines or bins, and 78.9% stored menstrual materials after their last period, often using appropriate wrapping. In a study by Deshpande et al., about 60% girls used sanitary pad and the rest used cloth pieces. About 22% used water and no soap for hand washing [14]. A similar trend was observed in the studies by Kansal et al., and Rokade et al., [15,16].

The majority of participants were under 16 years old, reflecting a critical stage in menstrual health awareness and practices. Older participants (16 years or more) demonstrated significantly better menstrual hygiene practices compared to younger counterparts. In a study by Khandaker et al., majority 23(51.11%) subjects were between 10 to 14 years of age with a mean of 14.42±1.03 years [17]. This finding aligns with existing literature suggesting that age and maturity play pivotal roles in adopting and maintaining proper hygiene behaviors [17,18]. Hindu participants constituted a significant majority (61.8%), followed by Muslims (35.4%) and others (2.9%). Religious affiliation emerged as a determinant factor, with Hindu participants exhibiting markedly better hygiene practices than Muslim and participants of other faiths. This discrepancy may stem from differing cultural norms and beliefs surrounding

menstruation, influencing attitudes and practices. A study by Sonowal et al., showed that Muslim religion has a significant association with knowledge regarding menstrual hygiene practices (OR: 2.846, $P < 0.05$) and sanitary disposal of absorbent by adolescent girls (OR: 2.528, $P < 0.05$) [19]. Such findings underscore the need for culturally sensitive menstrual health education programs tailored to diverse religious communities [20].

Participants predominantly belonged to nuclear families (77.5%), with mothers and fathers commonly having primary education backgrounds and engaging in home-making or daily-wage labor occupations. Family structure also played a crucial role, with participants from nuclear families reporting better hygiene practices than those from joint families. Nuclear families may offer more structured support systems and educational opportunities for menstrual health, contributing to improved practices among adolescents compared to their counterparts in joint family setups [21,22].

Maternal education levels varied, with primary education being the most prevalent (56.5%), while maternal occupations were predominantly home-makers (59%) and daily-wage laborers (23.9%). Maternal education levels significantly influenced menstrual hygiene practices, with higher education correlating with better practices among their daughters. Mothers with higher education levels are more likely to impart accurate knowledge and hygiene practices to their children, highlighting the intergenerational impact of maternal education on menstrual health [23,24].

Paternal education mirrored maternal patterns, with primary education predominating (55.4%), while paternal occupations were primarily daily-wage laborers (59.3%) and agricultural laborers (16.1%). Similarly, paternal education and occupational roles showed varied impacts on hygiene practices, indicating potential socio-economic influences. Fathers with higher education and certain occupational roles were associated with improved hygiene practices among their daughters, reflecting broader household dynamics and economic empowerment [25,26]. These findings underscore the complex interplay of socio-cultural factors, educational attainment, and family dynamics in shaping menstrual hygiene practices. Access to information, cultural beliefs, and socio-economic status collectively influence attitudes and behaviors towards menstruation and hygiene practices [27]. Addressing these factors through targeted educational interventions and community engagement is crucial for promoting equitable menstrual health outcomes across diverse populations [28]. Our study uniquely contributes insights into the nuanced roles of maternal and paternal educational backgrounds and occupational roles in shaping these practices.

Limitations: Limitations included the study's cross-sectional design and potential bias in self-reported data. Future research could employ longitudinal approaches and qualitative methods to explore deeper socio-cultural influences on menstrual health practices.

Conclusion

In conclusion, this study sheds light on the menstrual hygiene practices and knowledge among 285 adolescent students in the context of their demographic and educational backgrounds. The findings reveal a significant association between demographic factors such as age, religion, family type, and parental education with menstrual hygiene practices. Participants aged 16 or older, Hindus, and those from nuclear families demonstrated notably higher adherence to recommended hygiene practices compared to their counterparts. Moreover, maternal education level and occupation also played pivotal roles in shaping these practices. Despite high awareness levels regarding menstruation and hygiene products, a notable proportion lacked comprehensive knowledge about menstrual cycles and associated health risks. The study underscores the importance of targeted educational interventions and community awareness programs to bridge these knowledge gaps and promote consistent, hygienic practices among adolescent populations.

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